

MICROBIAL LANDSCAPE OF UNPACKED OPAQUE BEER SOLD IN BARS AND SHEBEENS; A CASE STUDY OF KABWE DISTRICT OF ZAMBIA

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ABSTRACT

For over a century, opaque beer has been regarded as a socio-cultural fermented beverage in many African countries that holds cultural meaning. In Zambia, this old-time fun favorite weak alcoholic beverage, highly popular among the old has been dated to have been first introduced in the 1950s way before the country attained its independence by Delta Beverages Breweries. In this study, we assessed the microbial load in opaque beer sold in bars and shebeens in Kabwe district of Zambia. The qualitative data were obtained by laboratory analysis. 38 samples were taken at random from bars and shebeens in the Kabwe district. Using conventional methods, the microorganisms were isolated and identified for Total viable count, coliforms, *staphylococcus aureus*, *E-coli*, yeast and molds. From the results, The PCA revealed that Total Coliform Count (TCC), *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E-coli* and Total Viable Count (TVC) were the most statistically significant factors ($p < 0.05$) influencing the microbial landscape. High positive

loadings for TCC (0.58824 on PCA 1) suggested coliform contamination as a primary driver of variability, indicating potential inadequate sanitation during production, processing or

handling. This was consistent with previous reports on fermented beverages. The significant contribution of *S. aureus* (0.79145 on PCA 2) highlights a substantial food safety concern, implying contamination from human handlers or unhygienic environments. TVC also significantly contributed to microbial differentiation, reflecting overall microbial activity. In contrast, *E. coli* and Yeast and Mold (YM) did not show statistically significant contributions ($p > 0.05$) to the primary components, suggesting their variability was not the main differentiator in this dataset. Furthermore, analysis of individual samples revealed significant variability, with sample 24 exhibiting the highest microbial load and sample 35 the lowest. This disparity underscores inconsistencies in production and handling. The findings collectively emphasize critical hygiene and food safety challenges in opaque beer production.

KEYWORDS: Microbial Load, Opaque beer, Kabwe district, Total viable count, Total Coliforms, *E.coli*, *Staphylococcus*, Yeast and Molds.

1. INTRODUCTION

For over a century, opaque beer has been regarded as a socio-cultural fermented beverage in many African countries that holds cultural meaning. In Zambia, this old-time fun favorite weak alcoholic beverage, highly popular among the old has been dated to have been first introduced in the 1950s way before the country attained its independence by Delta Beverages Breweries (Awe *et al.*, 2019). The procedure includes both alcoholic and lactic acid fermentation (Battcok *et al.*, 1998) Typically made from sorghum, millet, or maize, the end product of the brewing process is a pinkish-brownish liquid containing both dissolved and suspended particles (3.6% w/v), 3-5% alcohol, a pH of 3-4, and roughly 0.5 grams of lactic acid per liter with a substantial amount of protein and high carbohydrate content (Belay *et al.*, 2019; Braide *et al.*, 2024).

On a large scale, opaque beer is produced by well-established brewing companies whose customers are those from low-income neighborhoods. In Zambia such weak alcoholic drinks are common in mining towns and densely populated shanty compounds. Mostly thought of as a liquid food, the beer is also appreciated for its energy giving prowess (Campbell, 1994).

The production, packaging and eventual distribution of this liquid food is not without controversy. To start with, it is well known that even when acceptable levels of alcohol and lactic acid are reached, beneficial microorganisms used continue to grow which may result in spoilage of the product (Battcok *et al.*, 1998; Belay *et al.*, 2019; Braide *et al.*, 2024).

Packaging is another facet that continues to be a challenge for this product, while mandated by law to be sold in packs, it's a common sight to find the liquid food being sold in containers and being kept in dirty drums in most of these shebeens and tarven's as distributing companies usually supply this beer unpacked. In most cases in these bars and shebeens the liquid food stays for days under terrible conditions. In 2015, the Lusaka times, a Zambian news distribution platform ran an article captured "Bulk sale of opaque beer raises health risks". In this piece the sale of opaque beer in illegal unregulated bulk packaging was deemed to be a danger to public health by one of the countries' leading opaque beer brewer.^[1] This much needed warning at that time was attributed from National breweries who called on the local council to vehemently act on this habit.^[2] One can only wonder if maybe this message was reinforced with scientific evidence, then probably some action would have been done swiftly. In 2024, the Lusaka City Council (LCC) ventured on a robust enforcement of Statutory Instrument (SI) 23 of 2012 and SI 72 of 2012, two pieces which deal with a ban on the sale and distribution of bulk opaque beer.^[3] Accordingly, the LCC admitted to have gone into hibernation mode and were looking to make amends by curbing this vice due to a clear abrogation of food safety standards. It is interesting to point out that given the above time line and selective action, a simple visit to the bars and sheebens in 2025 paints a different picture, with one clear beaming message that the vice has not reduced and still poses a health hazard to the unsuspecting public. Perhaps such a timely scientific study providing evidence of the dangers of the sale and distribution of opaque beer in bars can fuel that dying local debate once more.

1. Daily Mail (2024). LCC gets tough on opaque beer. <https://www.daily-mail.co.zm/2024/02/21/lcc-gets-tough-on-opaque-beer/>
2. Lusaka Times (2015). Bulk sale of opaque beer raise health risks. https://www.lusakatimes.com/2015/10/20/bulk-sale-of-opaque-beer-raise-health-risks/#google_vignette
3. Delta Corporation Limited (2016). Annual report for 2016. <http://www.delta.co.zw/trad/chibuku>

A quick check on the shebeens and bars in Kabwe confirms that opaque beer is still a fun favorite although sold under unhygienic conditions. Many studies have highlighted the dangers that come from handling and sale of opaque beer under unhygienic conditions. For instance significant microbial load contamination has been identified in opaque beer with *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus spp* and *Salmonella spp* among those

identified as all due to poor or lack of good hygienic practice from the handlers while *Streptococcus spp* and *Candida spp* have been observed in other traditional opaque beer due to contamination (Egwurochi et al., 2021; Hiko et al., Jabloski et al., 1997). In another study, a microbial profile of an Ethiopian based household fermented opaque beer (Bubugn) revealed the presence of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Shigella* (Kadariya et al., 2014). Another type of creamy pinkish opaque beer in South Africa under the name of Umqombothi has previously been profiled to contain numerous pathogenic and spoilage microbes such as *Fusarium*, *Penicillium*, *Rhizopus*, *Proteus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Aspergillus*, *Bacillus*, and *Escherichia* while another similar study profiled Burukutu in Nigeria and identified six Gram-positive bacteria (*Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*) and six Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Enterobacter cloaca*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, and *Serratia marcescens*) were isolated from the Burukutu. Further *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Rhizopus*, and *Mucor* were among the isolated fungi (Katongole et al., 2008; Kutyauro et al., 2009). With this view in mind, it was imperative to conduct a microbial profile of opaque beer that is being sold in shebeens and bars in Kabwe district of Zambia.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Sample collection and examination

Opaque beer was randomly purchased from different sellers in Kabwe district. A total of 38 samples were aseptically collected and screened for microbial contamination.

2.2 Media Preparation

Specialized Agar Media: Agar plates with specialized media such as PDA for yeasts and molds, MSA for *staphylococcus aureus*, M-Endo Agar for coliforms and EMB for *E-coli* was prepared following the manufacturer's instructions.

2.3 Microbiological Testing

2.3.1 Total Viable Count

For The total viable counts, (TVC) pour plate technique was used. The samples underwent a serial dilution of 10^{-1} to 10^{-3} . Then, a 1 ml aliquot was inoculated on Nutrient agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37°C. Following incubation, distinct colonies that were formed were counted to obtain the CFU/ml.

2.4 Determination of Total Coliforms

M-Endo was used to obtain total coliforms by spread plate method. After serial dilution was conducted, a 0.1 ml aliquot was transferred to the plates and then later incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. All lactose fermenting colonies that appeared pink were counted and recorded as part of the total coliforms. The colonies were identified by morphological and biochemical characteristics using gram staining.

2.5 Determination of Yeast and Mold Count

Yeast and molds were isolated using potato dextrose Agar (PDA) using pour plate method. This was done by transferring 1mL of the homogenized sample on the petri dish. Also, 2-3 drops of acetic acid were added to the PDA to lower the pH of the media since fungi grow well in acidic environments. After that, the media was poured on the petri dish containing the sample. The plates were then incubated at 25°C for 3-5 days. After incubation, the plates were examined and the colonies that appeared fuzzy with a powdery texture with range of colors were considered as molds while those that appeared round, smooth and creamy white in color were considered as yeasts. The results were then recorded. For confirmation, microscopic examination with methylene blue was done for yeast and molds, showing typical of their morphology with branching hyphae and spores.

2.6 Determination of *Staphylococcus Aureus*

In the detection of *staphylococcus aureus* MSA was used by employing spread plate method. These were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The colonies were identified by morphological and biochemical characteristics using gram staining.

2.7 Determination *Escherichia Coli* (E. coli)

To detect *E. coli*, EMB agar was used by employing spread plate method. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The colonies were identified by morphological and biochemical characteristics using gram staining.

RESULTS

Table 1: Table of CFU/ml from 10^{-3} of various microorganisms grown from 38 opaque beer samples collected from bars and shebeens in Kabwe district of Zambia.

Sample	Total viable count	Total coliforms Count	Yeast and molds count	<i>E. coli</i> count	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> count	CFU/mL (TVC: 10^3)
1	84	13	45	8	33	8.4×10^4
2	160	27	62	10	71	1.6×10^5
3	92	41	42	2	47	9.2×10^4
4	76	28	18	15	20	7.6×10^4
5	183	5	24	0	59	1.83×10^5
6	82	17	8	13	63	8.4×10^4
7	93	0	31	0	51	9.3×10^4
8	64	0	14	0	84	6.4×10^4
9	102	21	47	9	81	1.02×10^5
10	231	15	66	7	19	2.31×10^5
11	96	16	41	11	31	9.6×10^4
12	180	23	53	5	57	1.8×10^5
13	104	34	20	13	69	1.04×10^5
14	78	18	33	6	57	7.4×10^4
15	157	31	62	17	45	1.57×10^5
16	153	22	41	8	76	1.53×10^5
17	85	26	34	15	51	8.5×10^4
18	177	41	38	11	66	1.77×10^5
19	241	20	17	9	81	2.41×10^5
20	138	3	55	0	98	1.38×10^5
21	97	0	31	0	43	9.7×10^4
22	261	13	44	8	56	2.61×10^5
23	130	20	31	14	105	1.3×10^5
24	275	55	77	34	78	2.7×10^5
25	104	37	63	42	55	1.05×10^5
26	112	59	88	12	27	1.12×10^5
27	281	66	41	27	44	2.81×10^5
28	132	21	38	9	61	1.32×10^5
29	286	8	30	0	90	2.86×10^5
30	273	77	44	0	15	2.73×10^5
31	120	4	12	0	88	1.2×10^5
32	77	0	56	0	34	7.0×10^4
33	154	38	32	14	18	154×10^5
34	81	11	41	5	27	8.1×10^4
35	122	6	33	0	130	1.22×10^5
36	88	0	25	0	43	8.8×10^4
37	125	15	33	9	74	1.25×10^5
38	113	28	22	11	31	1.13×10^5

3.1. Principle Component Analysis of isolated Microbes

Figure 1: Figure of Principle component analysis of microbial load from 38 samples from opaque beer collected from Kabwe, Zambia.

Figure 1: above shows the principle component analysis (PCA) of 38 samples collected from Various bars and shebeens from Kabwe Zambia. The above figure indicates different circles categorized as A, B, C, D, E and F. The above results represents samples that consist of the microbial load from the highest to the least. From the analysis, Circle F indicated the highest microbial load with sample 24 recorded as the highest followed by sample 27. Then, circle E came in second represented by sample 30 with its highest. Circle A represented samples with the least microbial load. Sample 35 from this circle had the least of all. The following analysis highlighted the diversity of each sample influencing the microbial landscape in opaque beer collected from different bars and shebeens. The data was analyzed using Genstats 18th edition (2015 version).

Table 2: PCA and Probability values of selected Microbes.

MICROBE	PCA1	PCA2	P-VALUE
<i>E-Coli</i>	0.49063	0.03108	>0.05
<i>Staphylococcus Aureus</i>	-0.25557	0.79145	<0.05
Total Coliform count	0.58824	-0.01412	<0.05
Total Viable count	0.36313	0.60783	<0.05
Yeast and Mold	0.46483	-0.05462	>0.05

The following table above indicates Microbes with different P values analyzed according to their different principal components. From the results, *E-coli* and Yeast and Mold had a p value >0.05 with the rest indicating a p value <0.05. The data was analyzed using Genstats 18th edition (2015 version)

3. DISCUSSION

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) conducted on the microbial populations in opaque beer samples revealed distinct patterns of microbial contribution to overall variation, with significant implications for product quality and safety.

The PCA results indicate that the Total Coliform Count (TCC), *Staphylococcus aureus*, and Total Viable Count (TVC) are the most statistically significant factors influencing the microbial profile of opaque beer. This finding is critical as TCC and *Staphylococcus aureus* are widely recognized as indicators of hygiene and potential public health risks, respectively. The strong positive loading of TCC on PCA 1 (0.58824) with a p-value of $P < 0.05$ suggests that coliform contamination is a primary driver of variability within the microbial communities. High coliform counts in fermented beverages often point to inadequate sanitation practices during production, processing, or handling (e.g., Orji et al., 2018; Awe et al., 2019). These findings were consistent with Ilango and Shankar (2018) who reported the presence of coliforms in fermented beverages. This also aligns with studies of Sterinkraus, (1996), who reported the survival of coliforms in acidic environments typical of fermented products emphasizing the association between poor hygiene and the presence of different microorganisms. This on the other hand is particularly concerning for opaque beer, which is often consumed without further heat treatment and may be produced under conditions that are less controlled than those for commercially bottled beverages.

Similarly, the highly significant contribution of *Staphylococcus aureus* (p-value <0.05), characterized by a strong positive loading on PCA 2 (0.79145), highlights a substantial food safety concern. *S. aureus* is a common human pathogen capable of producing enterotoxins that cause food poisoning, even when the organism itself is no longer viable (e.g., Jablonski and Bohach, 1997; Kadariya et al., 2014). Its significant presence in the PCA suggests a potential for contamination from human handlers or unhygienic environments during the brewing or dispensing process. This finding necessitates immediate attention to ensure that personnel involved in the production and distribution of opaque beer adhere to strict hygiene protocols. These results are consistent with Baeley, 2018 who studied the microbial profile

and contaminants of bubugn, an Ethiopian house hold fermented beverage, and uncovered the prevalence of pathogens like *Shigella*, *E.coli* and *S.aureus*. (Baeley, 2018).

The Total Viable Count (TVC), representing the overall microbial load, also emerged as a statistically significant contributor (p-value <0.05), with positive loadings on both PCA 1 (0.36313) and PCA 2 (0.60783). This indicates that the total number of microorganisms present is a fundamental aspect differentiating the samples, reflecting the overall microbial activity and potential for spoilage. While fermented products inherently contain high microbial loads (primarily yeasts and beneficial bacteria), an elevated TVC, especially when coupled with pathogenic indicators, can signify inadequate preservation or post-processing contamination (e.g., Battcock and Azam-Ali, 1998).

In contrast, *E. coli* and Yeast and Mold (YM) did not show statistically significant contributions to the major variations captured by the first two principal components (p-value >0.05 for both). Although *E. coli* is a crucial indicator of fecal contamination, its non-significant impact in this PCA (PCA 1: 0.49063, PCA 2: 0.03108) suggests that its variability across samples is not a primary factor distinguishing the microbial profiles in the dataset. This does not preclude its presence or importance as a direct indicator of fecal contamination, but rather indicates that other microbial groups, notably coliforms and *S. aureus*, are more influential in defining the overall microbial heterogeneity in this specific PCA model. Similarly, while yeasts are essential for fermentation and molds can indicate spoilage, their variability (PCA 1: 0.46483, PCA 2: -0.05462) was not statistically significant in this analysis. This could imply a relatively consistent yeast and mold population across samples, or that their variation is overshadowed by the more dynamic presence of coliforms and *S. aureus*.

Beyond the overall trends observed in the Principal Component Analysis, a detailed examination of individual sample microbial loads provides crucial insights into the variability and potential implications for opaque beer quality and safety. Our analysis revealed that sample 24 exhibited the highest microbial load, while sample 35 displayed the least. This wide range in microbial concentrations across samples underscores significant inconsistencies in either the raw materials, brewing process, handling, or storage conditions of the opaque beer.

The exceptionally high microbial load in sample 24 is a cause for concern. A high microbial load, encompassing Total Viable Count, often correlates with reduced shelf-life, increased spoilage potential, and a heightened risk of microbial instability (Campbell-Platt, 1994). When combined with the statistically significant presence of Total Coliforms and *Staphylococcus aureus* identified in the overall PCA, an elevated load in a specific sample like strongly suggests potential contamination events or inadequate control measures at some stage before sampling. This could range from poor raw material quality, insufficient fermentation control, unsanitary processing equipment, or post-production handling that introduces contaminants.

Conversely, the remarkably low microbial load in sample 35 is indicative of either a highly effective brewing and hygiene protocol, or perhaps even a product that has undergone some form of microbial inactivation, though the latter is less common for traditional opaque beer. A consistently low microbial load, especially for spoilage and pathogenic indicators, is desirable for product safety and extends shelf-life. This suggests that achieving a low microbial count in opaque beer is feasible and highlights best practices that could potentially be replicated across production batches.

The disparity between sample 24 and sample 35 emphasizes the heterogeneous nature of microbial quality in opaque beer and points to the urgent need for standardized production practices. Such variability implies that consumers could be exposed to vastly different levels of microbial risk depending on the specific batch or source of their opaque beer. Therefore hygienic practices need to be employed in the production processes just as suggested by Marsh & Bugusu, (2007) who highlighted the importance of packaging decisions and their impact on microbial load. Additionally by, Ogugbue, Mbakwem-Aniebo, and Akubuenyi (2011) whose studies were tailored to emphasis of the importance of packaging materials for handling, storage and transit.

Implementing stringent hygiene protocols, conducting regular microbial monitoring at critical control points, and ensuring proper storage conditions are paramount to minimize high microbial loads and enhance the safety and quality consistency of opaque beer across all production batches.

4. CONCLUSION

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on opaque beer samples has provided crucial insights into the microbial factors driving variation in product quality and safety. This analysis revealed that Total Coliform Count (TCC), *Staphylococcus aureus*, and Total Viable Count (TVC) are the most statistically significant contributors to the microbial profile, directly impacting public health and product integrity.

The prominent influence of TCC underscores widespread issues with sanitation during the production, processing, or handling of opaque beer, consistent with previous studies on fermented beverages. Similarly, the significant presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* highlights a serious health safety concern, indicating potential contamination from human handlers and emphasizing the risk of enterotoxin production. While TVC reflects the overall microbial load and spoilage potential, its elevated levels, particularly when coupled with pathogenic indicators, further signal inadequate preservation or post-processing contamination.

Conversely, *E. coli* and Yeast and Mold (YM) did not emerge as statistically significant drivers of major variations within this specific PCA model. This suggests that their variability, though generally important, was overshadowed by the more dynamic and defining presence of coliforms and *S. aureus* in the samples analyzed.

Furthermore, a detailed examination of individual samples revealed a wide disparity in microbial loads, with sample 24 exhibiting the highest and sample 35 the lowest. This stark contrast points to significant inconsistencies in raw materials, brewing processes, or handling and storage conditions. The high microbial load in certain samples is a cause for concern, indicating a heightened risk of spoilage and microbial instability, while the low load in others demonstrates the feasibility of achieving better control.

5. Recommendations for Enhanced Safety and Quality

In light of these findings, it is paramount that stringent hygiene protocols are implemented throughout the opaque beer production chain. This includes rigorous sanitation practices, consistent monitoring at critical control points, and ensuring proper storage conditions. Adhering to these measures is essential to minimize high microbial loads, enhance product safety and ensure consistent quality across all batches of opaque beer, ultimately safeguarding consumer health.

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